

قبل از اسلام بلوچستان میں تہذیب و مذاہب

Civilization and Religions in Balochistan before Islam**Muhammad Akbar (ORCID ID: 0009-0007-1919-5572)**

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ABSTRACT

Balochistan is one of the four provinces of Pakistan. It is the largest province in terms of land area, forming the southwestern region of the country. Balochistan shares borders with Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to the northeast, Sindh to the east and southeast, the Arabian Sea to the south, Iran to the west and Afghanistan to the north and northwest. Its area is 3,47,190 sq km, with the population of 1,23,44,408.

Historically, Balochistan has been a very imported region. The historical, political geographical and social status of the Balochistan region has always been recognized. Balochistan has been center of the oldest civilizations, in which there have been many rulers and invaders in different periods which dates back to Mad, Hinhamunshi, Greek, Moria, Sakka, Kishans, Han, Sassanic, Rai and Chach dynasties and families and they had left their effects on this region.

In Balochistan, before Islam various religions such as Christianity, Hinduism, Buddhism and Zoroastrianism etc have been inhabited. Even today, some religions except Islam still exist. Some of the relics of ancient religions still remain, including the Hindu temple of Kali at Kalat, Shiva Gee temple at Mastung, Mahadew's Astan at Hinglaj in Lasbella and Stadeeb's Astan in Makran are worth mentioning.

Keywords: Balochistan, History, Culture, Civilization, Religions, Archaeology.

کلیدی الفاظ: بلوچستان، تہذیب، تمدن، ثقافت، مذاہب، آثار قدیمہ۔

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